

Function as Use. Wittgenstein's Practical Turn in the Early Manuscripts

Florian Franken Figueiredo (University of Reading / State University of Campinas)

Department of Philosophy

Humanities & Social Sciences Building

Whiteknights

Reading RG6 6AA

f.figueiredo@reading.ac.uk

Abstract

The idea that the function of language is its use is commonly ascribed to the Later Wittgenstein. In this paper I argue that there is textual evidence already coming from the early manuscripts (Ms) proving that Wittgenstein's philosophical development is culminating in the idea of function as use around 1929-30. I interpret a passage from Ms-107 in order to show that Wittgenstein's practical turn has sources in different stages of his philosophical development, each of which is dominated by different ideas: the idea of a picture theory; the idea of a phenomenological language; and the idea of function as use.

In the February of 1929, Wittgenstein arrived back in Cambridge where he intended to return to those philosophical problems from which he had attempted to distance himself for several years. This time denotes the beginning of what is often called the 'middle period' in Wittgenstein's philosophical thought. In recent years the amount of literature regarding the middle period has increased, the focus of this literature being Wittgenstein's ideas about phenomenology.¹ The textual evidence for these ideas can be found in the only paper that Wittgenstein ever published, his 1929, 'Some Remarks on Logical Form'. However, the main sources are the first four volumes of his handwritten notebooks (Ms 105-108), containing remarks that were in part published posthumously under the title 'Philosophical Remarks' (hereafter PR). With reference to these and other sources, what is regularly discussed in the

¹ See e.g., Blank 2002, Casati 1995, Engelmann 2013, Hintikka 1996, Marion 2006, Munson 1962, Munz 2004, Noë 1994, Padilla Galvez 2008, Riuz Fernandez 2009, Soulez 1989, Stern 1995, Thompson 2008, and Venturinha 2012.

literature is the nature of what Wittgenstein called a ‘phenomenological language’, and there is considerable interest in how he abandoned this idea at the latest in October 1929. Comparatively little has been said, however, about the significance of this development, which constitutes Wittgenstein’s turn towards a practical view about the nature of language.

In this paper I discuss the textual evidence from the early manuscripts regarding Wittgenstein’s practical turn while also interpreting a passage from the manuscripts that correlates with a passage from the *Philosophical Remarks* starting between the middle of PR 58, §12 (a remark from Ms-107, 229) and the end of PR 60, §15. In interpreting this passage I intend to show that it has sources in different stages of Wittgenstein’s philosophical development. I argue that one may identify three stages, each of which is dominated by different ideas: the idea of a picture theory; the idea of a phenomenological language; and the idea of function as use. My aim here is to show how these ideas are related to the passage whose interpretation forms the focus of what follows. First, I argue that Wittgenstein changes the concept of the function of a word (as it is explained by the picture theory of the *Tractatus*) to the idea that the function of a word consists in its use. Second, I show that this idea is motivated by some of Wittgenstein’s own criticisms against the possibility of phenomenological language. Finally, I offer an understanding regarding remarks in Ms-107 that were recently interpreted as textual evidence for what is known as ‘Wittgenstein’s 1929 Pragmatism’. I argue that Wittgenstein was not outing himself in those remarks as an adherent to pragmatism. Rather, he uses a pragmatist view in order to develop his ideas further. Interpreting how the remarks fit into Wittgenstein’s development between 1929 and 1930 corroborates the interpretation of Wittgenstein’s pragmatism that I offer in this paper.

The context of the early manuscripts

After his return to Cambridge in January 1929, Wittgenstein recommenced writing down his philosophical thoughts in the form of short entries. His first entry is dated February 2nd, 1929. From then on he wrote them down in chronological order in large manuscript volumes that took the form of hard-covered notebooks. Although this chronicling of his remarks led to continuity in Wittgenstein’s writing, any systematic order that might have guided his thoughts is, at least on the face of it, hardly noticeable. Wittgenstein obviously did not intend to present his remarks in this form to a public readership.

However, around May 1930 Wittgenstein had to present his work to Bertrand Russell, who was supposed to write a report to the Council of Trinity College, Cambridge, in favour of a renewal of Wittgenstein's research grant. In his report, Russell wrote that Wittgenstein left him with, "a bulky typescript, *Philosophische Bemerkungen*, of which I have read about a third. The typescript, which consists merely of rough notes, would have been very difficult to understand without the help of the conversations."² The typescript that Wittgenstein had left with Russell consisted of a selection and rearrangement of passages that he had written in his first three manuscript volumes (I-III), and the first half of volume IV. He first dictated a typescript (Ts-208) from the passages in the manuscripts. Wittgenstein then made paper slips cut from this typescript and pasted them into a blank ledger in a new order. The result was the typescript (Ts-209) with the title 'Philosophical Remarks' that he gave to Russell³ and which was then edited and published posthumously by Rush Rhees. It contains remarks from the manuscript volumes written between 02.02.1929 and the last week of April 1930.⁴

Although Rhees disagrees in his *Editor's Note* with Russell's opinion that the typescript consisted of "merely rough notes", he points out that "it was not easy to read", referring primarily to the arrangement and unity of the work.⁵ With regards to its content, however, one may think of Rhees' judgment as an understatement. On the face of it, the remarks in the typescript present themselves to the reader in a rather wild and chaotic manner, giving the impression that they are assorted ideas on philosophical issues, as opposed to being thought-through lines of argumentation, organised with a reader in mind. From a certain perspective this might be seen as intelligible. In May 1930, that collection of remarks was assumed to be just what it appeared to be: a synopsis of his work; no more than a documentation of Wittgenstein's thoughts.

By the middle of the second half of 1929, Wittgenstein wrote up his remarks into what became the third volume (Ms-107) of eighteen large manuscripts.⁶ While he was working on this volume a rather unusual incident happened, owing to which Wittgenstein interrupted the

² Cf. Russell (1968: 196-200).

³ However, this reconstruction has been contested by some commentators, according to whom Russell read Ts-208 and not Ts-209; see McGuinness (2012: 182). Thanks to Anna Boncompagni for the pointer.

⁴ Hintikka and Hintikka (1996) point out, however, that, "this book cannot serve the same purpose as the notebooks [i.e., the manuscripts], because most of the traces of his [Wittgenstein's] earlier position and most of the traces of the painful struggle which was needed for him to overcome his earlier philosophical self have been removed from the more or less finished text of the book."

⁵ "Wittgenstein would not have published it without polishing. No spacing showed where a group of remarks hang closely together and where a new topic begins. Paragraphs were not numbered. And it was hard to see the arrangement and unity of the work until one had read it a number of times" (cf. PR, *Editor's Note*).

⁶ The first date that is mentioned in the third manuscript volume is 11.09.1929, written on page 87. Arguably, he started to write into the manuscript volume at the end of August or the beginning of September, 1929.

work after his entry on 04.12.1929 and continued writing in manuscript volume IV (Ms-108) on 13.12.1929. His reason, as he notes in the manuscript, was that he did not want to carry the third volume with him to Vienna, where he intended to spend Christmas with his fiancé, Marguerite, as well as meeting with Waismann and Schlick for conversations.⁷ He wrote his final remark on 05.01.1930 in Ms-108, 64. After he arrived back in Cambridge he continued writing his remarks into the third volume. The first entry after his return is written on 10.01.1930.

The first remark after Wittgenstein resumes writing in Ms-107 catches the attention since he there discusses the concept of function in relation to purposes for the very first time. The first thing that can be said about the discussion is that it draws an analogy between the ‘function’ of a word and the ‘function’ of an armchair, or a cogwheel, as they stand in relation to a purpose:

If we say ‘A word only has meaning in the context of a proposition’, then that means that it’s only in a proposition that it functions as a word, and this is no more something that can be said than that an armchair only serves its purpose when it is in space. Or perhaps better: that a cogwheel only functions as such when engaged with other cogs.

(Ms-107, 229; Ts-209, 5; PR 58, §12)

What more there is to say about this remark is less patent and as such should be viewed in the context of Wittgenstein’s intellectual development around the years 1929-1930. I suggest that three stages in his development should be considered as leading to this and the following remarks in Ms-107. Yet this suggestion has to be handled with care. As it shall become clear, it would be a misunderstanding to think that these respective stages can stand independently for themselves. However, one cannot pronounce with certainty upon when the development of one view begins or changes and when it is finished. Accordingly, these stages might be characterised, and thereby unified, by their overlapping aspects. These key aspects do not need to exclude each other. One might think here, as an analogous example, of the process of painting a picture. The painter usually does not produce the painting strictly from left to right but instead works on different parts at different times with different intensities. Analogously,

⁷ Cf. Monk (1990); see, especially, chap. 3. Wittgenstein met Waismann and Schlick six times during his visit, cf. Wittgenstein (1979).

the stages of Wittgenstein's development overlap rather than stand chronologically next to one another.

I suggest that according to the aforementioned key aspects the following stages can be identified: the first stage is dominated by the picture theory of the *Tractatus* and the idea that propositions are picturing facts, representing possible state of affairs while the function of a word is its meaning. The second stage is dominated by his conception of a phenomenological language and its critique by Wittgenstein himself, culminating in October 1929. Finally, the third stage, whereby Wittgenstein puts forward the idea that the function of words and propositions consists in their use. This stage begins on 10.01.1930 with the remark in Ms-107, 229. In what follows, I will put into context the three stages of Wittgenstein's development.

Regarding the context of the remark within the *Philosophical Remarks*, it seems that it belongs to a longer train of thought that starts with it (= PR 58, §12) and is then interrupted at the end of PR 59, §15.⁸ Owing to his technique of cutting paper slips from the typescript Ts-208 and pasting them in a new order, Wittgenstein composes them together in Ts-209, 4-5 with parts of Ms-108, 61-62 and 63 that he had written on 04/05.01.1930. Neither the break in his writings between January 5 and 10 nor the exchange of the two manuscripts is documented in the typescript. One can therefore only speculate about the reasons why Wittgenstein decides to put those remarks together. Yet it seems plausible to assume that they belong to a discussion regarding the "pictorial nature" of propositions. This is suggested by the following remark dated 03.01.1930:

If you think of propositions as instructions for making models, their pictorial nature becomes even clearer.

Since, for it to be possible for an expression to guide my hand, it *must* have the same multiplicity as the action desired.

(Ms-108, 58; PR 57, §10; original emphasis)

The main source of Wittgenstein's investigation into pictorial nature of propositions, of course, is his picture theory of the *Tractatus*. There, he explains the pictorial nature of the

⁸ In PR 58, §12, Wittgenstein introduces the possibility of a "naïve conception of the meaning of a word", based on the idea that someone imagines the meaning of a word when s/he hears or reads it. It seems that RP 60, §16 (= Ms-107, 235) connects seamlessly with this remark, which makes their connection to Ms-107, 229 even more puzzling. I therefore suggest we interpret the remarks beginning with PR 58, §12 until the end of PR 60, §15 as a parenthesis.

relationship between thought and reality and the conditions under which a proposition can be viewed as a logical picture.

Moreover, the analogy between the ‘function’ of a word and the ‘function’ of an armchair or a cogwheel as they stand in relation to a purpose in Ms-107, 229 is made against the background of a principle that forms one of the cornerstones of Wittgenstein’s picture theory: “A word only has meaning in the context of a proposition”. In the *Tractatus* (hereafter TLP), it is mentioned three times.⁹ At TLP 3.3, Wittgenstein writes: “Only propositions have sense; only in the nexus of a proposition does a name have a meaning.” At TLP 3.314, he repeats: “An expression has a meaning only in a proposition”; and in TLP 4.23 he adds that, “It is only in the context of an elementary proposition that a name occurs in a proposition.” In what follows I will briefly explain the idea behind the principle while referring to remarks that lead to its formulation in TLP 3.3. This will help to clarify the connection between the principle and the analogy mentioned at Ms-107, 229.

The first stage: Picture theory

In the *Tractatus*, the concept of a proposition and its relation to names is based on the concept of thought. Leading to the concept of thought is the idea that the world is a totality of ‘facts’ (TLP 1.1) and that we ‘picture’ these facts to ourselves (TLP 2.1). Pictures represent possible states of affairs. To be able to depict reality, i.e., a possible state of affairs, the picture must have a ‘logical form’ (TLP 2.18), and this leads to the idea that the logical picture of facts is a thought (TLP 3). The relation between thoughts and propositions is explained in the following way: “In a proposition a thought finds an expression that can be perceived by the senses” (TLP 3.1).

Thus, what is fundamental to the concept of a proposition and of thought, at least as it is introduced in the *Tractatus*, is that propositions are logical pictures of reality. Against this background, the nature of a proposition urges the following question: What are the conditions under which a proposition can be viewed as a logical picture? By giving an answer to it, Wittgenstein is aiming at the fundamental logic of depiction, including the logical

⁹ Apparently, this principle is influenced by Frege’s so called ‘context principle’, which, in variants, can be found five times in *The Foundations of Arithmetic*; see Frege (1995: x) and sections 46, 60, 62, 68. Is Wittgenstein simply endorsing the context principle? Baker and Hacker (2005: 161) point out that although he uses Frege’s terminology Wittgenstein “holds quite different principles concerning sense and meaning”. Happily, the deeper discussion of this question does not concern us here.

presuppositions that are essentially fulfilled by all representations (e.g., propositions, thoughts) of possible states of affairs. He is committed to the idea that, since they represent a state of affairs, all propositions share a common essence. As such, Wittgenstein wants to clarify what it is that is essentially shared by them (cf. TLP 5.4711).

What is essential to a representation can be viewed as the logical order of the picture or as rules of projection. It is important to understand that the relation between a representation and what is represented, between the picture and what it depicts, is an *internal* relation of the picture, i.e., what Wittgenstein calls its 'sense' (e.g., in TLP 2.221, 3.11, 3.13, 3.3). The internal relation consists in rules of projection that are essential to the picture as a picturing fact. Thus, the picture is a picturing fact only owing to the rules of projection, and only from the rules of projection can an external relation between the representation and the depicted state of affairs be derived. The logical order of a representation is preserved in the representation as a picturing fact and is in this sense essential to all representations of reality including propositions. While a picturing proposition represents a possible state of affairs in logical space, the place of the proposition in logical space is determined by the rules of projection. There is no projection without rules that determine the logical space. The place in the logical space must exist if what the proposition represents is possible (internal relation) and the proposition can then be compared with reality (external relation). This means in reverse that a proposition that is not projected onto reality by rules of projection is not a proposition or a sign of any language whatsoever. There is no proposition outside the logical space that is projected onto reality.

According to the *Tractatus*, a propositional sign is used as a projection of a possible state of affairs. A propositional sign that does not have sense cannot represent whatsoever and does not represent anything. It only represents insofar as it has sense, i.e., insofar as there is an internal relation between the proposition and what it represents. For example, the sentence 'My watch is on the table' can be used as a representation that represents a particular state of affairs, and it is projected onto reality by thinking of the sense of the proposition. The sentence only expresses a proposition with definite sense when it is projected onto reality. What the propositions project is a particular state of affairs, e.g., that my watch is on the table. However, the particular state of affairs is not itself included in the projection but only its possibility (TLP 3.13). Regarding the concept of a proposition as it is presented in the *Tractatus*, it is important to note that a proposition does not signify a particular state of affairs, but only that it involves the possibility of signification.

Thus, on the basis of the idea of propositions as logical pictures, we can better clarify the relation and difference between propositions and names. According to the *Tractatus*, propositions are picturing facts expressing a sense insofar as there are rules of projection determining their place in logical space. This involves determining the possible circumstances in which the proposition is true or false by combining its elements. In a logical picture the elements of the picture represent the objects in the world (TLP 2.13). They are the representatives of the objects. As I mentioned earlier, it is essential for a picture to have a logical order. Taking the elements of a picture into account, the internal relation of a picture can also be expressed by saying that what constitutes a picture is that its elements are related to one another in a determinate way (TLP 2.14). Accordingly, the external relation can be expressed by saying that since the elements of the picture are related to one another in a determinate way, this thereby *represents* that things are related to one another in the same way (TLP 2.15). The fact that the elements are related to one another determines the possibility within logical space that things in reality *are* related to one another in the same way, on the condition that the proposition is true. For example, if ‘*a*’, ‘*b*’ and ‘*xRy*’ are names that stand for objects then the combination of these names in the proposition ‘*aRb*’ shows how the represented objects in the world are related to another if the proposition is true (cf. TLP 3.1432).

The picture theory of the *Tractatus* is thus developed based on the idea of the logical form of a picturing fact, and so is the concept of a proposition and its elements. A proposition is only a proposition if it is projected onto reality by rules of projection. Although this idea presupposes possible states of affairs and objects in the world it would be a misunderstanding to interpret it as the attempt to deduce propositions and their elements from reality. Thinking about the logical form as something that is both shared by language and reality means to understand that their isomorphic relationship is based on the picturing fact and not on what is depicted. Wittgenstein attempts to clarify this in TLP 3.1432: “Instead of, ‘The complex sign “*aRb*” says that *a* stands to *b* in the relation *R*’ [this would be the assumption if *a* and *b* are ontologically presupposed as objects in the world], we ought to put, ‘That “*a*” stands to “*b*” in a certain relation says *that aRb*’ [while ‘*a*’ and ‘*b*’ are elements of a proposition that reaches out to reality]”.

If propositions only show that their elements are correlated to objects in the world but they do not say anything about the objects *themselves*, how can we then know about the objects that are represented by the elements in a proposition? The answer, I suggest, is that

independent of the picturing fact we cannot know anything about objects for which the elements stand.¹⁰ The picture is attached to reality owing to the logical form, that is, the internal relation, whereas it is owing to the correlation of the elements with things, that is, the external relation, that the picture ‘touches’ reality (cf. TLP 2.1515). These correlations are, as Wittgenstein puts it, the ‘feelers’ of the picture’s elements, whereby the picture ‘reaches out’ to reality. This idea does not suggest an ontological reading that assumes the existence of objects in the world independent of language on which elements of propositions with the same logical form are ‘docking’, as it were. It rather urges the view that objects are represented by the elements of a picture provided the picture has a logical form. External relations are based on internal relations, i.e., object-representing elements depend on the logical form of propositions. Wittgenstein remarks: “If everything behaves as if a sign had meaning then it does have meaning”. If a sign is not used in a representing system then it is *useless*, and “[i]f a sign is *useless*, it is meaningless” (TLP 3.328; original emphasis).

The relation between a proposition and its elements also clarifies the difference between them. Names and words are the constituents of propositions. Propositions are essentially the combination of their constituents in the sense that they cannot have a logical order or sense without their elements. On the other hand, it is only a proposition (amongst other pictures) that can have sense; names cannot. For example, it is deceptive, according to Wittgenstein, that in a printed proposition no essential difference is apparent between a propositional sign and a word (cf. TLP 3.143). But Wittgenstein is also clear that they must be distinguished, since the propositional sign is a picturing fact whereas a name is the representative of an object (TLP 3.22).

Objects are simple and so are names. Objects cannot be composite because they constitute the substance of the world. The argument for this claim derives from the idea that a state of affairs is a combination of objects that share logical form with a picturing fact. The picturing fact is essentially complex: if the picture is expressed by a propositional sign then the constituents of the complex are names that represent objects and the relation they stand to them. Both names and objects are combined in a logical form depicting a possible combination of objects and their relation in a state of affairs. Since only a picturing fact

¹⁰ I am following here the reading suggested by Marie McGinn, which is based on Winch (1987) and McGuinness (2002). According to her interpretation “[t]he object for which a name stands is not something that exists over and against language in an independent or transcendent realm, but is what we grasp when we grasp the meaning of the name, that is, when we grasp the contribution that the name makes to determining the sense of a class of propositions”; see McGinn (2006: 114). For a critical view of this interpretation see Zalabardo (2008).

expresses its sense in the form of a proposition constituted by the combination of names, it follows that facts can only be represented by propositions that have sense but not by given names (TLP 3.144). It follows, by contrast, that what can be named cannot be complex, i.e., it cannot be described by means of a proposition. While the contraction of a symbol for a complex can be expressed in a definition (TLP 3.24), a name that occurs in a proposition cannot be dissected any further by means of a definition. A logically simple name, as Wittgenstein puts it, is a “primitive sign” (TLP 3.26).

Why must a name be logically simple? We have seen that when a proposition represents a possible state of affairs in logical space, its sense is determined by rules of projection. Furthermore, the correlation of its elements with things is the means by which the picture reaches out to reality. If names were not logically simple the picture could not reach out to reality. Primitive signs would have no meaning and the sense of the proposition would be underdetermined. In this case, it could be stated hypothetically how the combination of elements and the possible state of affairs would be if elements were correlated with objects. If a picture does not reach out to reality, however, then it does not depict a particular state of affairs in the world that is either true or false. Thus, simple signs representing objects in the world must be possible for the complete determination of sense. As Wittgenstein puts it, the requirement that simple signs be possible is the requirement that sense be determinate (TLP 3.23). Since a picture must reach out to reality in order to have complete sense it thereby follows that objects cannot be described by means of propositions. If simple objects could not be represented by names, the answer to the question of whether a proposition has sense would depend on whether another proposition was true,¹¹ and hence the world would have no substance (cf. TLP 2.0211). Thus, if names did not stand for simple objects then whether a proposition had sense would depend on whether another proposition was true. As Wittgenstein remarks, “in this case we could not sketch any picture of the world (true or false)” (TLP 2.0212).

A proposition cannot determine the meaning of a primitive sign, it only determines the sign’s place in a system of representation. In order to determine the place of a primitive sign, its correlation with things in the world is required. The sense of a proposition, i.e., the possibility of representing a state of affairs, can only be determined by means of the picture’s

¹¹ This thought appears as the Tractarian version of the regress problem that the later Wittgenstein discusses with respect to rule following. The rules of projection that determine the sense of a proposition cannot be explained by the rules of projection of other propositions without getting into an infinite regress. See also Ms-104, 44 (= *Prototractatus* 3.20102): “The analysis of signs must come to an end at some point, because if signs are to express anything at all, meaning must belong to them in a way that is once and for all complete”.

‘feelers’ that reach out to reality. On the other hand, it is precisely the determination of a sign’s place in a system of representation by rules of projection that leads to the correlation of primitive signs with things in the world. A primitive sign has meaning when it is used in a proposition that has sense. Using signs in a proposition that depicts a possible state of affairs means, as we have seen, that the picture’s feelers reach out to reality.

However, this does not mean that the constituents of states of affairs for which names stand are described by means of propositions that are true or false. Although the existence of names is a logical necessity for the existence of propositions and thus the existence and non-existence of particular state of affairs, the correlation between a name and an object is independent of the particular state. Primitive signs stand for simple objects that are constituents of states of affairs in propositions describing those states of affairs. Those objects can only be named but they cannot be described by propositions. As Wittgenstein puts it, “[o]bjects can only be *named*. Signs are their representatives. I can only speak *about* them: I cannot *put them into words*. Propositions can only say *how* things are, not *what* they are” (TLP 3.221; original emphasis).

We may finish our brief discussion of Wittgenstein’s concept of names and propositions in the *Tractatus* by drawing the following conclusion. A proposition is a picturing fact insofar as it represents a possible state of affairs owing to the combination of its elements. However, a picturing proposition can only be projected onto reality if its sense is completely determined, which requires that its elements have meaning. Names have meaning insofar as they are correlated with objects for which they stand. While the correlation is a requirement for the proposition to determine its sense and thus a requirement for its constitution, it also depends on the proposition being constituted. The insight that objects are not *described* by propositions but *named* (while names are correlated to objects when they are elements of a proposition that reaches out to reality), leads to Wittgenstein’s following formulation of the principle that was aforementioned: “Only propositions have sense; only in the nexus of a proposition does a name have meaning” (TLP 3.3).

We may now come back to the remark in Ms-107, 229, and to the claim that if we say ‘A word only has meaning in the context of a proposition’, then that means that it is only in a proposition that it functions as a word. By contrast with the manuscript, it is striking that, while enunciating the principle in the *Tractatus*, Wittgenstein never mentions the word ‘function’. Instead he speaks about the ‘meaning’ of a name or expression, and the ‘occurrence’ of a name in a proposition. If one attempts to understand the word in the

framework of the picture theory of the *Tractatus*, then one may say that, if the meaning of the word is its function, and the function of a word is to represent an object in the world, then this function can only be realised within the context of a proposition. As we have seen, the reason for this is that a name can only be correlated to an object if it is an element in the proposition that represents a possible state of affairs. Thus, in order to accept this conception of the function of a word one has to accept the Tractarian conception of meaning, i.e., words having meaning insofar as they stand for objects.

However, it seems that in the remark from Ms-107, 229 Wittgenstein perceives a tension if one derives the concept of function from the principle. According to my interpretation, and recommended by the theoretical background implied by picture theory, I suggest reading the remark as follows: Wittgenstein (1) considers the account of meaning that he has presented earlier in the *Tractatus*. As we have seen, this account (2) implies the principle that a word only has meaning in the context of a proposition. Rather offhandedly, Wittgenstein then (3) introduces the assumption that the meaning of a word is its ‘function’. This (4) raises the question of what it means to say that a word has a function against the background of the aforementioned principle. The answer to this question (5) is that, according to the principle, the assumption that a word has a function implies that a word functions *only* in a proposition.

According to Wittgenstein, however, this conclusion seems to be utterly wrong. For to say that (i) a word has its function *only* in a proposition seems as mistaken as if one were to say that (ii) an armchair *only* serves its purpose in space (*im Raum*),¹² or that (iii) a cogwheel *only* functions as such when engaged with other cogs. The function of an armchair is not determined to serve its purpose in any kind of space (*Raum*). Similarly (and, according to Wittgenstein, “maybe better”), one might imagine different functions for a cogwheel than being engaged with other cogs. For example, one cogwheel might be separated from the others and used as a key holder, a bottle-opener, an ornament, or what have you.

¹² The English version of the *Philosophical Remarks* translates the German expression “im Raum” with “in space”. Wittgenstein uses the concept *Raum* while referring to things that are very different in kind, e.g., colours, expectations, memory, imagination, time, pain, etc. He also refers to different kinds of spaces e.g., Euclidean space, visual space, auditory space, physical space, space of muscular sensation, grammatical space, logical space, space of sight and movement, infinite space, feeling space, tactile space, etc. Moreover, he refers to the “present experience” as “something that isn’t *in* a space, but is itself a space” (PR 85, §54; original emphasis). Also Russell mentions in a letter to Moore that “Wittgenstein uses the words ‘space’ and ‘grammar’ in peculiar senses”; see Russell (1968: 198). Thus, if Wittgenstein speaks in Ms-107, 229 about space in an undetermined way I suggest that we leave it undetermined to what kind of space he is actually referring. In any case, the point that Wittgenstein is making here is that an armchair does not only serve its purpose when it is in space (irrespective of what kind of space is intended here).

A different way to interpret the remark is to put it in a continuous line with the Tractarian view about what can and cannot be said.¹³ According to this reading the principle that a word only has meaning in the context of a proposition cannot be said but only be shown because it is a kind of grammatical or tautological statement, just like the propositions that an armchair is an armchair only in space or that a cogwheel is a cogwheel only when engaged with other cogs. However, this line of interpretation would presuppose the assumption of Wittgenstein's attempt to defend the Tractarian view rather than the attempt to criticise it. If we go this way I am afraid that it becomes difficult to see how this line of interpretation is connected to the following remarks of the manuscript and to the concept of function that Wittgenstein is introducing here.

In contrast, I suggest that Wittgenstein's aims regarding the remark are the following two. The first aim is to show, by means of analogy, that words can be used like objects (armchairs, cogwheels, etc.) in *practical* contexts as opposed to the logical context of propositions. The second aim is then to show that, if the function of a word is understood as its use, then it cannot be restricted to the context of a proposition, as Wittgenstein held according to the principle of the *Tractatus*. But Wittgenstein goes a step further. He interprets the practical context of the function of a word not only insofar as the function of a word is its use, but also insofar as it instigates actions: "Language must have the same multiplicity as a control panel that sets off the actions corresponding to its propositions" (Ms-107, 231 = PR 58, §13).

What might have motivated Wittgenstein to make this step? I suggest interpreting this remark as an answer to the question of how the function of a word or sentence can be determined in a practical context.¹⁴ Language must have the same *multiplicity* as a control panel, but what restricts this multiplicity to the particular use of a word or sentence? According to the picture theory, the function of a word is determined by the sense of a proposition. This explains Wittgenstein's former claim that a word only functions in the context of a proposition, and we will need to return to it when we get into a deeper discussion on the nature of multiplicity to which Wittgenstein is referring. However, after the conception of function is changed to mean the use of a word, the question arises regarding how this function is to be determined if not by the context in which a proposition makes sense. The answer that Wittgenstein offers is that the use of a word or sentence is determined by the

¹³ This line of interpretation has been suggested by Severin Schroeder and Anna Boncompagni in private conversation. I am grateful for their suggestions and the opportunity to comment on them.

¹⁴ From here on, I shall use the word 'sentence' instead of 'proposition' when I talk about its function as use. The fact that both can be translated with the German word 'Satz' presents a notorious problem for Wittgensteinian commentators.

purposes that those words or sentences are used for. He suggests that in practical contexts the purpose of a word or sentence is to instigate actions.

The second stage: Phenomenological language

This suggestion seems to be motivated, in addition, by Wittgenstein's former discussions regarding the possibility of a phenomenological language—an idea that dominates the second stage in his philosophical development. In what follows I shall explain this view beginning with the assumption that the purpose of a word or sentence is to set off actions. This assumption raises questions regarding the relationship between use and purpose, and also between sentences and actions. In the *Tractatus*, propositions are related to possible states of affairs by representing them, and they can be said to be either true or false after being compared to them. As Wittgenstein remarks at Ms-108, 58 (= PR 57, §10), “pictorial nature becomes even clearer” if we think of propositions as something action-guiding, e.g., as “instructions for making models”, or as “an expression to guide my hand”. Thus, he thinks that propositions must also represent the possible actions corresponding to them (cf. Ms-107, 289; PR 63, §21), and that pictorial nature becomes particularly clear in such practical contexts. In sum, actions are part of a reality onto which propositions must latch.

However, the relationship between language and action reveals a problem for Wittgenstein that he had dealt with during the time of his arrival in Cambridge in February 1929 until October 1929. During this time, Wittgenstein struggled with the idea of a ‘phenomenological language’, that is, a language describing the actual phenomena of our experience. One reason why he believed in this idea is that he was convinced that *only* by means of the analysis of our everyday language could we derive a clear logical structure that excludes pseudo-propositions and the ambiguous application of expressions. In ‘Some Remarks on Logical Form’ from 1929, Wittgenstein argued that we are not able to draw conclusions regarding the actual logical form of phenomena from norms pervading our ordinary language “into which we project in *ever so many different ways ever so many different* logical forms”¹⁵. In conversations with Schlick and Waismann in December 1929, he expounded his view as follows:

¹⁵ Wittgenstein (1929: 164); original emphasis. See also Ms-107, 281.

I used to believe that there was the everyday language that we all usually spoke and a primary language that expressed what we really knew, namely phenomena. I also spoke of a first system and a second system.¹⁶

In order to understand Wittgenstein's statement, we must first consider the relation between phenomenological language and the propositions of the *Tractatus*. According to the picture theory, the reality that propositions reach out to is the physical reality that includes single objects and states of affairs. Since the author of the *Tractatus* does not distinguish between different kinds of propositions in terms of immediate experience, it might seem as if the propositions that picture immediate experience must be handled in the same way as those that picture other possible states of affairs in reality. But a closer look reveals that there are differences between them, in specific owing to the immediate nature of phenomenological experience.

The first difference regards logical form. As Wittgenstein points out in 'Some Remarks on Logical Form', immediate experience implies logical forms (e.g., colours, sounds, etc.) that have "very little similarity with the logical forms of our ordinary language".¹⁷ The second difference regards the 'primacy' of immediate experience. While ordinary language describes the 'physical world'¹⁸ of objects that appear along the physical dimensions of space and time, phenomenological language describes what he calls the 'primary world' of immediate experience that appears in the form of sense data.¹⁹ With this terminology Wittgenstein does not intend to say that the primary world and the physical world do not belong to the same reality. He in fact emphasises that while both phenomenological language and physical language describe the same reality (cf. Ms-105, 108; Ms-105, 122; Ms-107, 3), they describe it in different logical forms and even for different purposes (cf. PR 99, §71). The third difference regards the comparison of language with reality. Phenomenological language describes immediate experience in the world of sense data, while this experience, owing to its immediate nature, cannot be false. If immediate, phenomenal experience cannot be false, it follows that the phenomenological language that describes it must be necessarily true, and thus there is no sense in which both language and reality are to be compared. Phenomenology, as Wittgenstein puts it, "aims at sense and not at truth" (Ms-105, 3). As such, the goal of

¹⁶ Wittgenstein (1979: 45).

¹⁷ Wittgenstein (1929: 165).

¹⁸ Cf. Ms-107, 160; Ms-108, 28. Wittgenstein also speaks about the 'ordinary physical language' or the 'normal physical language'.

¹⁹ Cf. Ms-105, 108. Wittgenstein also occasionally calls it the 'world of data'; cf. Ms-105, 86; Ms-105, 96.

phenomenological language is merely to describe what is possible, i.e., what makes sense, since the question of whether *what* it describes is true does not even arise. Thus, phenomenological language does not imply hypotheses about whether those possibilities are actually the case or not. Physical language, however, must also be able to map on to reality, implying, therefore, hypotheses about this reality. Propositions involving physical language must either be true or false.

The assumption that phenomenological language and physical language describe reality in different logical forms leads Wittgenstein to speak of a ‘first system’ and a ‘second system’. It seems that Wittgenstein’s terminology refers to two different systems of representation.²⁰ In the first (‘primary’) system, the phenomenological language describes the sense data of the primary world. In the second system, physical language describes objects and states of affairs along the physical dimensions of space and time. However, Wittgenstein eventually becomes aware that the assumption of a primary system of representation in which language describes the immediate character of reality is incoherent, and that a phenomenological language is not possible.

What, however, is incoherent about the idea of a primary language? To begin with, the idea has two flip sides. First, it assumes immediate experience in a world of sense data describable in a primary language. Second, it assumes that a primary description of immediate experience *can actually be given*. Both assumptions reveal problems that Wittgenstein discusses in the manuscripts. The first problem is that speaking about the present appearance of an immediate experience leads to a paradox. On the one hand, it seems that the experienced phenomenon appears in time. This is suggested by its appearance in the present and how we talk about it. One cannot speak of immediate experience that appears in the present if the world of data is timeless. It is also suggested by the assumption that the experienced phenomena are necessarily true. Even though the experience of sense data cannot be false they must have been verified. And if immediate experience is not verified *in the present* then what kind of alternatives are there? On the other hand, it seems that the phenomenon cannot appear in time since it appears immediately, thereby excluding that it appears either in the past or in the future.²¹ What underlies the attempt to describe the phenomenological character of reality is the temptation to think that this reality only exists in the present moment. But the thought that

²⁰ Nowhere in the manuscripts does Wittgenstein explain explicitly what the first and the second system refer to. Hintikka and Hintikka 1996, n.3 assume that, “[b]y the first (primary) system Wittgenstein meant the phenomenological one, by the second (secondary) one the physicalistic system of concepts (language).”

²¹ Cf. Ms-105, 114; PR 98, §69: “Isn’t it like this: a phenomenon (specious present) contains time, but isn’t in time? Its form is time, but it has no place in time.” See also 107, 6-7; PR 104, §75.

immediate experience exists in the present is specious since speaking of the *present* experience only makes sense if we can put it in temporal contrast, that is, referring to the past or the future. It follows that ‘phenomenological reality’ means something *excluding* temporal contrast, something that “isn’t in a space but is itself a space”, as Wittgenstein puts it. As such, the word ‘present’ is needless (if not misleading) when we refer to immediate experience.²²

Nevertheless, it seems that the world of sense data is continuous and does not tear off. We are thus inclined to think that “everything flows” (cf. Ms-108, 1; Ms-108, 26; Ms-107, 1-2; Ms-107, 159), while holding the idea that the present is continuously disappearing. But how can we make sense of this idea if speaking of our immediate experience excludes contrasting it with the past or the future? Moreover, if we assume that immediate experience in a world of sense data can be described in a primary language, yet the words of the description (e.g., ‘present’) do not refer to time, we may ask with Wittgenstein: “Is there time in the first system at all?” (cf. Ms-105, 84).

The assumption that phenomenological language does not include hypotheses about whether the description is actually verified by an event but merely *describes* the verifiable event suggests that the primary language does not require time. For example, at Ms-105, 108-112 (= PR 97, §67), Wittgenstein considers a description according to the memory of all his sense impressions, which would in fact be a biography. He then raises the question: “[W]hy shouldn't I be able to leave everything hypothetical out of this description?” In order to have “the most immediate description we can possibly imagine” he would rebuild the visual images plastically, “with plaster-cast figures on a reduced scale”, representing them “to two eyes fixed at the particular place in the model”. However, to produce the representation he would need to construct the description according to his memory, and so this would be hypothetical after all—or so it would seem. Moreover, we might assume that the model is moved by a mechanism that could be set into proper motion with a crank drive.²³ This assumption makes clear that even the most immediate description involves time:

²² Cf. Ms-108, 1; PR 85, §54: “We are tempted to say: only the experience of the present moment has reality. And then the first reply must be: As opposed to what? [...] If someone says, only the *present experience* has reality, then the word ‘present’ must be redundant here, as the word ‘I’ is in other contexts. For it cannot mean *present* as opposed to past and future.—Something else must be meant by the word, something that isn't *in* a space, but is itself a space. That is to say, not something bordering on something else (from which it could therefore be limited off). And so, something language cannot legitimately set in relief” (original emphasis). See also Wittgenstein (2005: 495).

²³ Cf. Wittgenstein (2005: 492): “this machine could be set into proper motion with a crank drive, and by turning the crank, we could read off the description. (An approximation to this would be a representation in film.)”

We could imagine that the mechanism could be driven by turning a crank and in that way the description ‘read off’.

What we understand by the word ‘language’ unwinds in physical time. (As is made perfectly clear by the comparison with a mechanism.)

(Ms-105, 112; PR 97, §67/Ms-105, 114; PR 98, §69)

Note that this conclusion is consonant with Wittgenstein’s assumption that propositions represent the possible actions corresponding to them. For setting the mechanism into proper motion with a crank drive is an action corresponding with the biographical description read off of the mechanism. When the visual images are moved by the mechanism, which thereby *produces* the description, the description requires time. Any attempt to circumvent this requirement by being more immediate would not lead to a description of the phenomena but rather to inarticulate sound.²⁴ Wittgenstein’s following remark puts this more pithily: “You simply can’t begin before the beginning” (Ms-105, 114; PR 98, §68).

The conclusion that any description of immediate experience, even the most immediate description we can possibly imagine, must necessarily have a temporal form leads to a second problem that Wittgenstein addresses: “If the world of data is timeless, how can we speak of it at all?” (Ms-105, 96; PR 80, §48). If phenomenological language necessarily requires time, how can there be descriptions of timeless phenomena? The assumption was that descriptions in the second system represent physical objects and states of affairs, whereas descriptions in the first system represent immediate experience in the world of sense data, i.e., timeless phenomena. This distinction now leads to a problem. Since any description must have a temporal form, it is clear that “language itself belongs to the second system”. As Wittgenstein explains: “If I describe a language, I am essentially describing something that belongs to physics” (Ms-105, 114; PR 98, §68; cf. Ms-108, 60; Wittgenstein (2005: 494)).

The problem indicates that the distinction between two different systems of representation is somehow misguided. In order to see what is causing the confusion, Wittgenstein suggests the following analogy to illustrate the description of immediate experience and the description of physical objects²⁵:

²⁴ Another possible reaction to the model would be to “just stare at it intently”; cf. Stern (1995: 141).

²⁵ The importance of this analogy in Wittgenstein’s thought is also highlighted in Stern 1995; see, especially, chap. 5. See also Schulte (2006).

If I compare the facts of immediate experience with the pictures on the screen and the facts of physics with pictures in the film strip, on the film strip there is a present picture and past and future pictures. But on the screen, there is only the present.

(Ms-105, 84-85; PR 83, §51)

Both the pictures in the film strip and the pictures on the screen represent the same reality, but they describe it in different forms. The pictures in the film strip describe reality in a temporal order so that it makes sense to say that next to the present picture there are past and future pictures to which they stand in a temporal relation. In this sense the description of the pictures can be compared with a description of physical language. Looking at the pictures on the screen, however, one only sees what is pictured in the very moment, and one is therefore inclined to say that the pictures describe “only the present”.

We have seen already that this expression leads to a paradox. This is because it suggests, on the one hand, that the pictures on the screen are presented in the present time while, on the other hand, the form of their appearance excludes temporal order. Furthermore, Wittgenstein’s analogy helps us to understand how an attempt to describe immediate experience leads into such entanglement. Wittgenstein points out that, “with our language we find ourselves, so to speak, in the domain of the film, not of the projected picture” (Ms-108, 2; PR 98, §70; cf. Ms-107, 176). Since any language essentially describes something belonging to physics we apply the concept of physical time in order to describe immediate experience while mapping it on to reality. But this attempt is misguided. This is because its corollary is contradictory, namely that timeless phenomena appear in the present. This conceptual confusion consists in mistaking our ordinary physical language with a falsely assumed primary language, i.e., the confusion of the second with the first system:²⁶

It's strange that in ordinary life we are not troubled by the feeling that the phenomenon is slipping away from us, the constant flux of appearance, but only when we philosophize. This indicates that what is in question here is an idea suggested by a misapplication of our language.

²⁶ It is often assumed that Wittgenstein’s turning point was in October 1929; see e.g., Hintikka and Hintikka (1996), and Hintikka (1996). The manuscripts provide textual evidence, however, that Wittgenstein is already aware of this confusion when he begins to write his entries into the third manuscript volume (Ms-107), e.g., pp. 1-2 (written before 11.09.1929); 160; 176; 205 (dated 25.11.1929). He continues his criticism in Ms-108, e.g., pp. 29 (dated 21.12.1929); 31-32; 60 (dated 03.01.1930).

The feeling we have is that the present disappears into the past without our being able to prevent it. And here we are obviously using the picture of a film strip remorselessly moving past us, that we are unable to stop. But it is of course just as clear that the picture is misapplied: that we cannot say ‘Time flows’ if by time we mean the possibility of change. What we are looking at here is really the possibility of motion: and so the logical form of motion.

(Ms-108, 27; Ms-108, 32-33; PR 83, §52)

An entanglement caused by confusing the first and second systems also threatens a reconsideration regarding the relationship between language and action. Against the background of the *Tractatus*, one might assume that the logical possibility of a proposition belongs to the first system, i.e., the primary world of which we have immediate experience, whereas the action as it is performed takes place in physical time. In particular, one might think that the multiplicity of a word, in order to be used, must be understood along the same lines as the logical possibility of a proposition’s capacity to represent.²⁷ If it is a presupposition of the function of a word that it can be used in multiple ways can this multiplicity be understood along the same lines as the internal relations of a proposition?

On the assumption that the multiplicity of use is similar to the logical possibility of a proposition, it follows that it belongs to the first system. But this conclusion leads to puzzlement. For how can the understanding of an action lead to the actual performance of the action? The understanding does not appear in a temporal order but rather immediately, whereas the action is performed in time. While Wittgenstein had already discussed the assumption of a primary language in previous months, in January 1930 he notices that the problem the question addresses, “is again one of the relationships between the I. & II. system” (Ms-107, 231). However, given his previous discussion of the problem, Wittgenstein is able to avoid the conceptual confusions suggested by the question that is raised. He explains that:

[w]hen I speak of words & their syntax then this happens “in the II.” and this also must hold when I speak of symbolizing relationships between propositions and

²⁷ Cf. Wittgenstein (1979: 84ff): “A very good method of illustrating the representational character of language consists in understanding the propositions of our language as *instructions* for doing something. [...] Here it is completely clear that language must have the same multiplicity as the movements that I direct by my propositions. All you do must already be contained in what I say. (If I am to make a machine work at three different speeds, I cannot possibly achieve this by moving a lever that has only two positions.)” (Original emphasis).

facts. I.e., we are speaking here again of something which is extended in time & not instantaneous.²⁸

(Ms-107, 232)

Thus, regarding the relationship between language and action, Wittgenstein's insight that language belongs to the second system is equally important. As Wittgenstein makes clear with reference to the model that gives the most immediate description of his sensations, it would be a mistake to think that there is a categorical difference in terms of a first and second system, that is, between language in which the description is given and the action corresponding to it. For turning the crank and thereby moving the model is precisely the action corresponding to the description read off from the mechanism.

The insight thus leads us back to Wittgenstein's practical view that the function of a word or sentence is its use, which is related to a purpose. This function may be viewed analogously with the function of control panels and handles in a control room:

Just as the handles in a control room are used to do a wide variety of things, so are the words of language that correspond to the handles. One is the handle of a crank and can be adjusted continuously; one belongs to a switch and is always either on or off; a third to a switch which permits three or more positions; a fourth is the handle of a pump and only works when it is being moved up and down, etc.; but all are handles, are worked by hand.

(Ms-107, 232; PR 58, §13)

As we have already observed, Wittgenstein's practical view intends to clarify the relation between words and objects and the function of a word, emphasising that the function of a word is its use. Words are used like handles in a control room. Each handle has a certain function: it functions as a crank, a switch, a pump, etc. Furthermore, the functions are related to different purposes, i.e., different handles are used to set off different things. This view assumes that the function of a word has a similar multiplicity to the function of a handle, rather than, as the *Tractatus* holds, that the word has only one function, namely to be correlated to a particular object, as determined by the sense of the proposition. The function must include the multiplicity of all purposes that the word or sentence can be used for, while the *actual* function is determined by the purpose it is actually used for.

²⁸ This and the former remark written on 12.01.1930 are not transferred to the *Philosophical Remarks*. They are quoted here according to my translation.

The third stage: Function as use

As we have seen, Wittgenstein's practical view changes the perspective of the principle according to which a word only has meaning in the context of a proposition. At Ms-107, Wittgenstein describes the new perspective by means of an analogy between the use of a word and the use of a rod. It is in the context of use that a word or sentence has a certain function, as it is within use that the rod has a certain function, for example the function of being used as a lever. Accordingly, to say that a word functions in the context of a proposition means to say that a word functions in the context of *using* a word or sentence. This is analogous to saying that the function of a rod is it to be used as a lever:

A word only has meaning in the context of a proposition: that is like saying only in use is a rod a lever. Only the application makes it into a lever.

(Ms-107, 233; PR 59, §14)

An important aspect to the view that Wittgenstein returns to is the relationship between the multiplicity of function, i.e., the multiple ways of using a word or sentence, and the actual use as it is related to a purpose. In the *Tractatus*, a word's function contributes to the sense of a class of propositions that are determinately either true or false. Thus, what is required of a proposition, according to the picture theory, is its *logical* possibility. The practical context of a proposition, however, seems to imply different requirements. Under the assumption that words are used with a certain function, their applications must not only be possible but, more strongly, for a word to have meaning it is also required that it is *actually* applied. Wittgenstein emphasises that, "[a]ll of this has to do with questions of possibility – a possibility that never becomes actual" (Ms-107, 233-234). The passage in full runs as follows:

[a] That this paper could be black is shown by the fact that the proposition "it is black" is false.

[b] Isn't it required that I must remember how black looks like in order to give sense to this proposition?

[c] The application of words considered as extended in time is easy to understand; in contrast, I find it infinitely difficult to understand the sense in the moment of application.

[d] What does it mean e.g. to understand a sentence as a member of a system of sentences?

[e] (It's as if I were to say: the use of a word isn't over in an instant, any more than that of a lever).

[f] Imagine a gearbox whose lever can take four positions. Now of course it can only take these positions in succession, and that takes time; and suppose it happened that it only ever occupied one of these positions, since the gearbox was then destroyed. Wasn't it still a gearbox with *four* positions? Weren't the four possible?

[g] Anyone who saw it would have seen its complexity, and its complexity is only to be explained by the use for which it was intended, to which in fact it was not put. Similarly I would like to say in the case of language: What's the point of all these preparations; they only have any meaning if they find a use.

[h] Is one allowed to say: The sense of a proposition is its purpose? (Or, of a word 'Its meaning is its purpose'.)²⁹

Arguably, Wittgenstein is pointing out a tension here between the concept of sense, as it can be found in the *Tractatus* on the one hand, and the practical application of a proposition, i.e., its practical context on the other hand. According to his earlier view, the sentence, 'This paper is black', for instance, expresses a proposition that has sense only if it belongs to a class of propositions that can either be true or false. The meaning of 'black' in this proposition only requires the possibility of the proposition being either true or false, i.e., it requires that the paper *can* be black. If this possibility is the only requirement for understanding the proposition then it follows that the proposition can also be understood if the proposition will never be true. But this is hardly conceivable since it is required that one must remember how black *looks* in order to give sense to the false proposition. The sense of a proposition cannot depend on the possibility of representing a particular state of affairs since there cannot be any understanding of its elements if the proposition were never true.

²⁹ Ms-107, 233-234; original emphasis. Paragraphs *a*, *b*, *c* are not transferred to the *Philosophical Remarks*. Paragraphs *c* and *d* are quoted according to the translation in Stern 1995, p. 139, paragraphs *a* and *b* are quoted according to my translation. The rest of the passage can be found in PR 59, §15. Paragraph *d* is slightly modified there and combined with paragraph *e*. Furthermore, it is particularly interesting that in the manuscript paragraph *h* was formulated first as a question (as it may be found in my translation). In PR 59, §15 Wittgenstein says: "You might say: The sense of a proposition is its purpose. (Or, of a word 'Its meaning is its purpose'.)"

Moreover, as we have seen in the discussion regarding the possibility of a phenomenological language, in order to understand the proposition, ‘This paper is black’, it is not sufficient that the proposition is true *in the moment* of application, i.e., owing to immediate experience. As Wittgenstein argues, a primary language of sense data is not possible since language itself belongs to physics. Thus, against the background of picture theory, it is not only “endlessly difficult” to grasp the meaning of words in the moment of their application, but it is rather impossible. The logical possibility that the object it represents *can* occur in a possible state of affairs would be independent of time, whereas physical language unwinds temporally. However, if we understand, as Wittgenstein explains, that “the use of a word isn’t over in an instant, any more than that of a lever”, then we will see that the application of words considered as extended in time, i.e., as part of physical language, is easily understood.

The practical view of a word’s function, and the analogy of the rod that functions as a lever, clarify this point. Let us imagine a gearbox whose lever can take four positions. We would say that this lever has the possibility of four applications. Owing to this, one might think that the understanding of the lever’s applications in the gearbox is provided by the logical possibility of the lever’s positions, i.e., the positions the lever can take. But it must be taken into account that the lever can only take those positions, and be so applied, in succession. It is the actual application of the lever that takes time. Taking this crucial aspect into account, Wittgenstein argues against the view that the *possible* application is a sufficient requirement for understanding. For, if we imagine that the lever only ever occupied one of these positions, and if the gearbox was then destroyed, could we still say that it was a gearbox with *four* positions? Against this background it is difficult for somebody to mean what they say when they claim that there were four possible positions in the gearbox. One might respond that the complexity of the gearbox is only to be explained by the use for which it was intended (i.e., the possible positions that the lever could have taken), though it never in fact took these positions. For, as the *Tractatus* argues, the logical possibility of the proposition is presented as a *preparing* condition for the proposition’s possible comparison with particular states of affairs. However, Wittgenstein’s criticism against this former view holds that the possibility is insufficient to guarantee the understanding of a proposition and its elements. If sentences are supposed to provide understanding then the preparing conditions required for propositions to have sense miss the point. For, as Wittgenstein points out, “they only have

meaning if they find a use.” The principle that a word only has meaning in the context of a proposition must therefore be viewed from a practical perspective:

If one – as I have suggested a long time ago – composes propositions of things like chairs, tables etc. rather than of printed words it becomes particularly clear in which sense “words only have meaning in the context of a proposition”.

The question ‘What is a word?’ is completely analogous with the question ‘What is a chessman?’

(Ms-107, 240; cf. TLP 3.1431; PR 61, §18)

In the first remark, Wittgenstein is asking about the sense in which the concept of a proposition is to be understood if it is composed by objects like chairs and tables. In the *Tractatus*, he wrote that: “[t]he essence of a propositional sign is very clearly seen if we imagine one composed of spatial objects (such as tables, chairs, and books) instead of written signs” (TLP 3.1431). In the manuscript, he returns to this earlier formulation. However, he now argues that the picture underlying this statement has to be changed. As the example of the lever makes clear, spatial objects, like chairs and tables, have certain practical functions. They play a practical role in an arranged context, for example in a gearbox or in the dining room. On the basis of this practical view, Wittgenstein appears to suggest in the second remark an analogy between the way in which words stand in the context of a proposition and the way in which objects stand in a practical context, for example in the context of a chess game. In contrast to the view that a class of propositions representing a particular state of affairs determines the meaning of words, words become meaningful when they are applied with a practical function in the context of a sentence.

However, the view that the actual use of a sentence is its function raises the question of how the sense of a sentence is to be conceived of from a logical point of view. Logic is supposed to answer the question of how the sense of a proposition, or the meaning of a word, is to be determined. However, if the sense of a sentence and the meaning of a word depend on their actual function, i.e., the way that they are used in certain circumstances, then it seems odd to draw the conclusion that logic is concerned with the natural history of use. Wittgenstein’s own doubts against his developing practical view indicate that he is still struggling with the Tractarian picture of logic. As a result, he raises the question at Ms-107,

234 whether, “one [is] allowed to say: The sense of a proposition is its purpose? (Or, of a word ‘Its meaning is its purpose’.)”³⁰

One week later, on January 20 1930, the day after Frank Ramsey dies and also the day of his first lecture in Cambridge, Wittgenstein gave his answer to this question. In the remainder of this paper I shall discuss some of the entries of this day (Ms-107, 247-250) that lead to his answer. They begin with an insight that should be familiar to the reader by now, namely that the sentences we use in our everyday lives operate differently to what, in logic, is meant by propositions. This insight, as we have seen, is based upon the distinction between two different conceptions of function. Sentences we use in our everyday life have a different function than propositions. Nevertheless, one might say that they share a hypothetical character: sentences are hypothetical insofar as they serve the purpose for which they are used (“[e]vents do not seem to verify or falsify them in the sense that I [i.e., the author of the *Tractatus*] originally intended”), while propositions that represent possible state of affairs are hypothetical insofar as they might be true or false³¹.

It has been argued recently that Wittgenstein’s changing perspective regarding the hypothetical character of sentences is influenced by the pragmatist view held by Frank Ramsey³². According to this view, hypotheses are habits by which we meet the future. Owing to this, it is assumed that Wittgenstein is close to a pragmatist view when he writes:

When I say ‘There is a chair over there’, this sentence refers to a series of expectations. I believe I could go there, perceive the chair and sit on it, I believe it is made of wood and I expect it to have a certain hardness, inflammability etc. If some of these expectations are disappointed, I will see it as proof for retaining that there was no chair there.

Here one sees how one may arrive at the pragmatist conception of true and false: A sentence is true as long as it proves to be useful.

(Ms-107, 248)

³⁰ The fact that Wittgenstein is struggling with this question becomes less clear at PR 59, §15, since none of the remarks from Ms-107 between 19.01.1930 and 26.01.1930 (including Ms-107, 234) were transferred.

³¹ I am in agreement here with Boncompagni (2016: 17) who points out that “Wittgenstein clearly distances himself from a certain vision of logic and shows an interest in the ordinary use of language”.

³² For a pragmatist interpretation of Wittgenstein’s remarks in Ms-107, 247-250 see, e.g., Misak (2016), especially, chap. 7; Boncompagni (2016, 2017, and forthcoming). What I name the ‘third’ stage in Wittgenstein’s development is called ‘Wittgenstein’s 1929 Pragmatism’ in Misak (2016). In the text I shall refer to her translation of the remarks.

In general, I am sympathetic to the idea that a possible source of Wittgenstein's practical view might be Ramsey's pragmatism. This would help trace the genesis of Wittgenstein's claim that the concept of function is to be understood as use. I am, however, not convinced that the remark in the manuscripts suffices as textual evidence of Wittgenstein's pragmatism. To the contrary, it does not recommend the conclusion that Wittgenstein himself adopted a pragmatist view.³³ The primary reason for my objection is exegetical. The fact that Wittgenstein shows "how one may arrive at the pragmatist conception" does not thereby imply that his own position is pragmatist³⁴. Moreover, there is evidence that Wittgenstein did not want the quoted remark to be transferred to the *Philosophical Remarks* or any other typescripts that he later produced. Indeed, he rejected that his way of doing philosophy was connected to *any* theoretical approaches—any 'isms', as it were. Accordingly, he would have refused to be called an adherent of pragmatism.

Thus, instead of going as far as assuming that Wittgenstein outs himself as a pragmatist in his remark from 20.01.1930, I suggest that the reason why he takes Ramsey's view of hypotheses as an alternative concept is that, during his intellectual development, Wittgenstein learned to appreciate the issues encountered by his earlier conception. As we have seen, his views about sense data and immediate experience, which Wittgenstein had defended before September 1929, required that they be understood as non-hypothetical representations. But Wittgenstein noticed that if this assumption holds, then:

the representation loses all its value if the hypothetical element is dropped, because then the proposition does not point to the future any more, but it is, as it were, self-satisfied and hence without any value.

(Ms-107, 249)

Wittgenstein's discussion regarding the possibility of a primary language shows that propositions belonging to this kind of language are not hypothetical since they are not

³³ Misak (2016: 241) argues that Wittgenstein adopts Ramsey's position regarding the concept of hypothesis that the latter defends in his paper, 'General Propositions and Causality', in particular the view that "a variable hypothetical is not 'strictly' a proposition at all, but 'a formula from which we derive propositions'". Although this might have well been the case, it does not imply that Ramsey's adopted pragmatism was Wittgenstein's *only* reason to take the position, and so he might not have been convinced of pragmatism as such. We have seen other good reasons why, during his development, Wittgenstein was not able to hold earlier positions, and he might have therefore been open to alternative views on particular issues. Notwithstanding this attitude, this alone does not make Wittgenstein a pragmatist. For a similar view see Preston (2017).

³⁴ Boncompagni (2016: 20) also acknowledges that "[i]n this remark there are no value judgments regarding pragmatism: Wittgenstein simply mentions it".

compared with reality. This means that they do not represent anything in the sense of the picture theory because they would need to represent a possible state of affairs, i.e., something that may either be true or false. Similarly, sentences that we utter in everyday life do not represent anything if they are understood as non-hypothetical. For example, in our understanding of an action we would not be able to represent the action if it was not possible that the action could ever be performed. The sense data that the person has of that action (for example, owing to imagination or memory) would be, as Wittgenstein puts it, “self-satisfied and hence without any [representational] value” (ibid).

Does the same hold if the function of the sentence is considered as its use? Wittgenstein remarks that, “[e]very sentence we utter in everyday life appears to have the character of a hypothesis”. The reason for this is, as we have seen, that their function needs to be related to a purpose determining what their function *is*. For example, if the function of a cogwheel is not determined by a particular purpose, it can thereby be used for everything and nothing. In case a sentence is not used for a particular purpose, we might at best give the explanation that the use itself is the purpose, i.e., that the use of the sentence is an *end-in-itself*. In this case, however, the sentence in everyday life would be self-satisfied like the proposition in logic, even though the underlying concept of function is quite different. If the use of the sentence is an end-in-itself, however, then it is clear that the sentence lacks instrumental value. Or, to put it differently, if the function of a sentence is not related to a purpose then it cannot be used as an instrument, and would not have any meaning. Accordingly, Wittgenstein points out:

It makes no sense to speak of sentences, if they have no instrumental value.

The sense of a proposition is its purpose.

When I tell someone ‘There is a chair over there’ I want to produce in him certain expectations and ways of acting.

(Ms-107, 249-50)

From Wittgenstein’s comparison of the hypothetical character of a proposition (an issue, as we have seen, that he was concerned with in his second stage) with the hypothetical character of a sentence (an issue that was raised by the practical view of the function as use), we may draw the following conclusion. If we are looking for non-hypothetical representation, then, on the one hand, propositions in logic do not have representational values since they can only picture possible state of affairs that can be compared with reality. On the other hand,

sentences used in our everyday life do not have instrumental value under those circumstances, since they can only function if they are related to purposes.

As a result, it seems that the understanding of a sentence involves the agents' intentions and expectations as they are directed towards the purpose of that sentence. For example, if the sentence, "There is a chair over there", has a certain function, then it is used with a certain intention to fulfil a particular purpose, while it may also raise the expectation that the uttering of the proposition fulfils a particular purpose, e.g., to alert someone to the possibility of sitting down. Since a proposition has no sense without an intended purpose, it is constitutive of the use of language that the function of a proposition is combined with a particular purpose, which is intended and which might also be expected. Wittgenstein thus emphasises that, "[i]f you exclude the element of intention from language, its whole function then collapses" (Ms-107, 289 = PR 63, §20).

The practical view, then, holding that the function of sentences is related to purposes, implies the possibility that those purposes can be intended and expected. This raises the question of how one can know about those purposes and their relationship to the function of sentences. How can one know which purpose is related to the use of a word or sentence, i.e., which purpose fulfils certain intentions and expectations? This question concerns Wittgenstein's discussion of intentionality that we unfortunately cannot deal with in this paper. Needless to say, by the time of the *Philosophical Investigations* Wittgenstein had dealt with the problems connected to this issue, having developed an understanding of intentionality that is itself worth exploring³⁵.

References

Baker, G. P. and Hacker, P. M. S. (2005). *Wittgenstein. Understanding and Meaning*, second extensively rev. ed. Malden: Blackwell.

³⁵ An earlier version of this paper was presented at the Wittgenstein Forum in October 2017 at the University of Reading. I would like to thank the participants and, especially, Severin Schroeder, John Preston, and Anna Boncompagni for very helpful comments and suggestions. I also thank the State University of Campinas and the University of Reading for having me as visitor during the academic year 2017/2018. Finally, I would like to express my gratitude to the Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (FAPESP) for the generous financial support of my visit (Grantnr: 2017/05530-9).

- Blank, A. (2002). "Wittgenstein's *Tractatus* and the Problem of a Phenomenological Language". *Philosophia* 29: 327-41.
- Boncompagni, A. (2016). *Wittgenstein and Pragmatism*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Boncompagni, A. (2017). "The „Middle” Wittgenstein (and the ‘Later’ Ramsey) on the Pragmatist Conception of Truth". In C. Misak and H. Price (eds.), *The Practical Turn: Pragmatism in the British Long 20th Century*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 29-44.
- Boncompagni, A. (forthcoming). "Wittgenstein and Pragmatism: A Neglected Remark in Manuscript 107 (1930)". In M. Baghramian and S. Marchetti (eds.), *Philosophical Revolutions: Pragmatism, Analytic Philosophy and Phenomenology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Casati, R. (1995). "Notes on Phenomenology and Visual Space". In R. Egidi (ed.), *Wittgenstein: Mind and Language*. Dordrecht: Kluwer, pp.185-192.
- Engelmann, M. L. (2013). *Wittgenstein's Philosophical Development: Phenomenology, Grammar, Method, and the Anthropological View*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Frege, Gottlob (1959). *The Foundations of Arithmetic*, second rev. ed. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Hintikka, K. J. J. (1996). "The Idea of Phenomenology in Wittgenstein and Husserl". In J. K. K. Hintikka, *Ludwig Wittgenstein: Half-Truths and One-and-a-Half Truths: Selected Papers, Volume I*. Dordrecht: Kluwer, pp. 55-77.
- Hintikka, K. J. J. and Hintikka, M. B. (1996). "Wittgenstein's *annus mirabilis* 1929", In J. K. K. Hintikka, *Ludwig Wittgenstein: Half-Truths and One-and-a-Half Truths: Selected Papers, Volume I*. Dordrecht: Kluwer, pp. 107-124.
- Marion, M. (2006). "Phenomenological Language, Thoughts, and Operations in the *Tractatus*". In R. E. Auxier and L. E. Hahn (eds.), *The Philosophy of Jaakko Hintikka*. LaSalle: Open Court, pp. 413-430.
- McGinn, M. (2006). *Elucidating the Tractatus. Wittgenstein's early philosophy of language and logic*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- McGuinness, B. F. (2002). "The Supposed Realism of the *Tractatus*". In B. F. McGuinness, *Approaches to Wittgenstein*. London: Routledge, pp. 82-94.
- McGuinness, B. F. (2012). *Wittgenstein in Cambridge – Letters and documents 1911-1951*. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Misak, C. (2016). *Cambridge Pragmatism: From Peirce and James to Ramsey and Wittgenstein*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Monk, R. (1990). *Ludwig Wittgenstein: The Duty of Genius*. New York: Free Press.

- Munson, T. N. (1962). "Wittgenstein's Phenomenology". *Philosophy and Phenomenological Research* 23: 37-50.
- Munz, V. A. (2004). "Phenomenology and Language: Some Remarks on Wittgenstein's Middle Period". In J. C. Marek and M. E. Reicher (eds.), *Experience and Analysis: Papers of the 27th International Wittgenstein Symposium*. Kirchberg am Wechsel: Austrian Ludwig Wittgenstein Society, pp. 255-257.
- Noë, R. A. (1994). "Wittgenstein, Phenomenology, and what it Makes Sense to Say". *Philosophy and Phenomenological Research* 54: 1-42.
- Padilla Galvez, J. (2008). "Phenomenology as Grammar". In J. Padilla Galvez (ed.), *Phenomenology as Grammar*. Frankfurt: Ontos Verlag, pp.7-14.
- Preston, J. (2017). "Misak Cheryl, Cambridge Pragmatism: From Peirce and James to Ramsey and Wittgenstein". *Philosophical Investigations* 40: 443-448.
- Ruiz Fernandez, J. (2009). "Wittgenstein's Phenomenology and Wittgenstein's Phenomenological Relevance". *Polish Journal of Philosophy* 3: 17-27.
- Russell, B. (1968). *The Autobiography of Bertrand Russell*, Vol. 2. London: Allen and Unwin.
- Schulte, J. (2006). "Wittgenstein on Time (1929-1933)". In F. Stadler & M. Stölzner (eds.), *Time and History: Proceedings of the 28th International Ludwig Wittgenstein Symposium, 2005*. Frankfurt: Ontos Verlag, pp. 557-67.
- Soulez, A. (1989). "Wittgenstein and Phenomenology Or: Two Languages for One Wittgenstein". In B. F. McGuinness & R. Haller (eds.), *Wittgenstein in Focus – Im Brennpunkt Wittgenstein*. Amsterdam: Rodopi, pp. 157-183.
- Stern, D. (1995). *Wittgenstein on Mind and Language*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Thompson, J. M. (2008). *Wittgenstein on Phenomenology and Experience: An Investigation of Wittgenstein's 'Middle Period'*. Bergen: Publications from the Wittgenstein Archives at the University of Bergen, No. 21.
- Venturinha, N. (2012). "Wittgenstein on Heraclitus and Phenomenology". In I. Somavilla and J. M. Thompson (eds.), *Wittgenstein und die Antike/Wittgenstein and Ancient Thought*. Berlin: Parerga, pp. 85-110.
- Winch, P. (1987). "Language, Thought and World in Wittgenstein's *Tractatus*". In P. Winch, *Trying to make sense*. Oxford: Blackwell, pp. 3-17.
- Wittgenstein, L., Luckhardt, C. G. and Aue, M. (2005). *The Big Typescript, TS. 213*, German-English scholar's ed. Malden: Blackwell.

- Wittgenstein, L. (1979). *Ludwig Wittgenstein and the Vienna Circle: Conversations Recorded by Friedrich Waismann*. Edited by B. F. McGuinness, translated by J. Schulte and B. F. McGuinness. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Wittgenstein, L. (1975). *Philosophical Remarks*. Edited by R. Rhees, translated by R. Margraves and R. White. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Wittgenstein, L. (1971). *Prototractatus*. Edited by B. F. McGuinness, translated by Pears and McGuinness. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.
- Wittgenstein, L. (1929). "Some Remarks on Logical Form". *Proceedings of the Aristotelian Society*, Suppl. Vol. 9: 162-171.
- Wittgenstein, L. (1961). *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus*. Translated by David Pears and Brian McGuinness. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- Zalabardo, J. L. (2008). "Elucidating the "Tractatus": Wittgenstein's Early Philosophy of Logic and Language by Marie McGinn". *Mind* 117: 1105-1108.